
Implementation of the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 19 of 2016 concerning the Smart Indonesia Program

(Study at the Education Office in Bojonegoro Regency)

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Abstract: *Education in Indonesia is the responsibility of the Ministry of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia. Education in Indonesia is regulated by Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System. The government issued Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 19 of 2016 concerning the Smart Indonesia Program. This study aims to find out how to implement the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 19 of 2016 regarding the Smart Indonesia Program in Bojonegoro Regency. The theory used in this research uses the theory of George Edward III with a descriptive qualitative approach. To achieve these objectives using data collection methods by observation, interviews, and documentation. The results of this study indicate that. There are four factors that influence the implementation of the policy, namely Communication in the delivery of the Smart Indonesia Program, Resources consisting of (human resources, infrastructure resources, and budget resources), Disposition and Bureaucratic Structure. Regulations and implementation of the education office divide the tasks in implementation according to the level of education in the Bojonegoro Regency Education Office so that policies do not overlap with other parties.*

Keywords: *Policy Implementation, Smart Indonesia Program, Financial Assistance.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Education in Indonesia is education whose entire implementation is in Indonesia, both structurally and non-structurally. Residents in Indonesia are required to follow the compulsory education program for basic education for nine years, six years in elementary school and three years in junior high school. Education in Indonesia is regulated in Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System. Currently, there is still a lag in the quality of education either formally or informally. Education is the main support in increasing Indonesia's human resources in nation building. The lack of equitable distribution of education results in the lagging of the quality of education. Equitable education is important in a democratic climate, where the nation's children need to receive a proper education so that there is no discrimination.

The government issued Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 19 of 2016 concerning the Smart Indonesia Program, which is assistance in the form of cash from the government given to students who cannot afford education costs. Smart Indonesia Card is a card given to children aged 6 (six) years to 21 (twenty one) years as a marker or identity to get the benefits of the Smart Indonesia program. The Smart Indonesia Program is expected to guarantee the right to obtain proper education up to high school level for poor or underprivileged families. The cost of education is a crucial problem for some people, especially those with lower middle economic levels.

The Bojonegoro Regency Government has implemented the Smart Indonesia Program. The education office of Bojonegoro Regency is in charge of providing financial assistance for the Smart Indonesia Program based on data obtained from the Social Service Office as a data collector on which parties need this social funding assistance, then the data collection obtained will be screened by the Ministry of Education and Culture regarding who will enter quota of beneficiaries for the Smart Indonesia Program. However, the Smart Indonesia Program in Bojonegoro Regency at this time, the disbursement of the Smart Indonesia Program funds is not complete, students who receive Smart Indonesia Cards are not on target, there are still parents who receive Smart Indonesia Cards who do not manage the Smart Indonesia Program aid funds properly, the community is less involved in the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program, and most people do not understand the policies and mechanisms for distributing funds for the Smart Indonesia Program. (www.beritasatu.com)

As for research on the Smart Indonesia Program, where this study analyzes the policies of the Smart Indonesia Program at the elementary school level (Lilis Novia, 2017), research that analyzes the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program through the 2015/2018 Smart Indonesia Card at SMA Negeri 11 Yogyakarta City.(Agus Styani, 2017).From this research, there are various approaches applied to research government policies. The results of this study indicate that the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program policy at the elementary school level in the city of Samarinda has not run optimally, with factors that hinder the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program policy so that it is not in accordance with the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program. In research on the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program at SMA Negeri 11 Yogyakarta City, there are inhibiting factors, namely the lack of communication between channeling institutions and schools related to taking funds, lack of budget for socializing the Smart Indonesia Program and data accuracy. This research is different from the above study, using an approach and focusing on junior high schools as a whole in Bojonegoro Regency.

There is a purpose in this study to find out how to implement the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture Number 19 of 2016 concerning the Smart Indonesia Program (Study at the Education Office in Bojonegoro Regency) and to describe how the Smart Indonesia Program goes from the center to the regions, especially in Bojonegoro Regency. The benefits of this research are expected to increase knowledge, contribute and be able to add to the literature on study materials related to the Implementation of the Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 19 of 2016 concerning the Smart Indonesia Program.

II. METHODS

This research use descriptive qualitative approach. Qualitative research is a research method based on postpositivism, which is used to examine the condition of natural objects (as opposed to experiments) where the researcher is the key tool, data collection techniques are carried out in a combined manner. In analyzing using interactive data analysis techniques Miles and Huberman's model, which states that "activities in qualitative data analysis are carried out interactively and take place continuously until complete. Activities in data analysis, namely data reduction, data display and conclusion drawing/verifying" (Sugiyono in Suprastiyo, 2021). This research focuses on the theory presented by Geroge Edward III 1980 namely Communication, Resources, Disposition and Bureaucratic Structure in the policy implementation process. Data collection techniques in this study were carried out by observation, interviews, and documentation. In this study, three informants were used, namely key informants, main informants and supporting informants.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Bojonegoro Regency has an area of 230,706 Ha, with a population in 2018 of 1,311,042 people, and in 20219 of 1,331,077 people. Based on the results of the study, it shows that in the regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 19 of 2016 concerning the Smart Indonesia Program, cash assistance from the government is given to students whose parents are less able to finance their education. Students try to develop their potential through the learning process available at certain paths, levels, and levels of education.

Communication in the Smart Indonesia Program uses socialization methods, both online and offline. Offline socialization was carried out after the results of socialization from the center with socialization materials in the form of the Smart Indonesia Card Policy, BRI regulations and Integrated Social Welfare Data. Online socialization is done through cellphones and laptops. Dissemination of information to the public about the Smart Indonesia Program with the aim that the public understands the purpose of the Smart Indonesia Program assistance program. The level of education in Bojonegoro Regency is classified as good but there are still some people who are classified as low due to the economic situation. The division of tasks has been in accordance with the main tasks and functions of each concerned. As well as, 1 Chief Executive in charge of coordinating implementing members and implementing operators. The implementing member of the Smart Indonesia Program is in charge of supervising and providing information to the recipients of the Smart Indonesia Program. Eko Purnomo as a basic education staff stated:

"We are delivering information on the Smart Indonesia Program in stages, I am waiting for information from the center, after information from the center of the education office proceeds to phase 2 where the education office holds a meeting first regarding the decision of the Smart Indonesia Program from the center to continue the Smart Indonesia Program to candidates. We convey information to schools by dividing the related tasks to disseminate information on the Smart Indonesia Program for elementary and junior high schools. After the information arrives at the school, the school will collect data regarding the potential recipients of the Smart Indonesia Program, after which the education office waits for the data on the prospective student recipients of the Smart Indonesia Program to be sent to the Ministry of Education and Culture. (Interview with basic education staff Eko Purnomo, 26 July 2021).

Resources in the Smart Indonesia Program to support the Smart Indonesia program, there are six employees who handle the Smart Indonesia Program out of 89 total employees at the Education Office. The six employees have their respective positions, namely the secretary of the education office, with two members who have the positions of head of the education sector and head of the student section. There are three operators, namely two employees as staff in the field of basic education and one member as staff in the PNF field. Eko Purnomo as a basic education staff revealed that:

"In the course of the Smart Indonesia Program, there is an implementing team that has been arranged by the Bojonegoro Regency Government Education Office which has been determined by the head of the Bojonegoro Regency Education Office". (Interview with basic education staff Eko Purnomo, 26 July 2021).

Facilities and infrastructure in carrying out the Smart Indonesia Program The Education Office uses facilities, 1 laptop where the laptop is to access the data of recipients of the Smart Indonesia Program candidate which will be sent to the Directorate General of Education, 2 cellphones, the use of cellphones here is to provide information to parties related to the Program Smart Indonesia includes those who run or accompany the recipients of the Smart Indonesia Program candidates (executive members) and so on and 3 printers, the printer uses here to print letters, where the printed letters will be sent to the intended school according to the duties of each operator. Based on the researcher's interview with the Basic Education Staff, said that:

"Yes, ma'am, in the course of the Smart Indonesia Program from the Education Office which is in charge of implementing the Smart Indonesia Program, it uses 3 cellphone facilities, a laptop and only tools for printing letters". (Interview with basic education staff Eko Purnomo, 26 July 2021).

The Education Office's budget source for the Basic Education Staff section does not issue any budget at all. Furthermore, for the budget from the center according to the data provided per student or student, following the budget per student year. The Smart Indonesia Program given by the Ministry of Education and Culture for programs in the Bojonegoro Regency area which is then followed up by the Bojonegoro Education Office from 2018 to 2021 has different values. in 2018 it was worth 43,078,500,000 then in 2019 it increased which was

worth 46,316,225,000 However, in 2020, during the pandemic, the Ministry of Education and Culture decided to reduce the budget given, which was worth 39,469,175,000 then for 2021 it was worth 20,567,025,000

The regulations used in the Smart Indonesia Program use the regulations of the Secretary General of the Ministry of Education and Culture regarding Amendments to the Regulation of the Secretary General of the Ministry of Education and Culture Number 3 of 2021 concerning Implementation Guidelines for the Smart Indonesia Program for Basic and Secondary Education. This Smart Indonesia Program Regulation prioritizes Smart Indonesia Card holders which are the results of the latest data collection between students registered in Dapodik and DTKS, students with orphan and orphan status, students who have just returned to school due to dropping out of school, the impact of natural disasters, victims of disasters in conflict areas, disabilities and students whose parents are prisoners in correctional institutions.

The Smart Indonesia Program mechanism at the district level is carried out by the Education Office and is determined by the composition of the membership and the Smart Indonesia Program at the Ministry of Education Office at the Education Unit level is carried out by the Smart Indonesia Program team at the Education Unit Education Unit. In implementing the Smart Indonesia Program, the government created a coordinating team at every level of education, starting from Elementary School, Middle School and Equality Education. Eko as the Basic Education Staff who handles the Smart Indonesia Program for Elementary and Middle Schools. He said that:

“So the implementation team was formed to run the Smart Indonesia Program. Which is run by 6 people and in each of us there is someone who takes care of Elementary Schools, and Junior High Schools, to disburse the Smart Indonesia Program funds”. (Interview with basic education staff Eko Purnomo, 26 July 2021).

Based on the results of the interview above. The implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program, the Bojonegoro Regency education office, is still lacking in providing information to the people of Bojonegoro Regency. It can be seen from the statement of one of the informants interviewed by the researcher. It is proven by the many complaints and protests from the public against the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program carried out by the Education Office of Bojonegoro Regency. In addition, there are still delays in the disbursement of funds for the Smart Indonesia Program.

In a program the bureaucratic structure can affect the implementation of a program. As for the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program carried out by the Bojonegoro Regency Education Office, the bureaucratic structure is 1) Proposing the Acceptance of the Smart Indonesia Program. 2) Management of Funds for Candidates for the Smart Indonesia Program at the Ministry of Education. 3) Determination of Smart Indonesia Program Recipients Ministry of Education 4) Determination of Smart Indonesia Card Recipients. 5) The distribution of funds for the Smart Indonesia Program related to the Smart Indonesia Program from the middle school SMPNegeri3 Bojonegoro said that:

“In the course of the Smart Indonesia Program from this school, it is very supportive, on the other hand prospective students who want to get the Smart Indonesia Program we provide ways for students to get the Smart Indonesia Program, including prospective recipients must collect a family card, after that we send it to the education office and waiting for further confirmation for anyone who will get an account card to receive aid funds from the Smart Indonesia Program”. (Interview with Mr. Roli as a BK teacher at SMP Negeri 3 Bojonegoro (give guidance) 2 Thursday 2021).

“In this Smart Indonesia Program, my son got the program. Because I am a private worker (small trader), before my child can get the Smart Indonesia Program, there are requirements that must be submitted to the school, namely a family card and a certificate of incapacity.” (Interview with Ms. Pu'ah as the student's guardian, 3 Friday 2021)”.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Second, resources are divided into 3, namely 1 human resources, namely the education office of Bojonegoro Regency which has the authority in carrying out the implementation or as an implementer, then non-formal resources, namely in the form of funds provided by the government to support the implementation process. 2 facility resources, namely to assist implementation in running the Smart Indonesia Program. 3 budget resources, namely assisting the implementation process in supporting implementation or financing students who have Smart Indonesia Cards or students as recipients of the Smart Indonesia Program. The third is Disposition where in terms of disposition, in this program the education office divides tasks for implementation or implementation according to the level of education in the Bojonegoro Regency Education Office. Fourth, namely the bureaucratic structure where in terms of this bureaucratic structure is the organizational structure of achieving the goals of a program in achieving it. The bureaucratic structure is very influential on the implementation of the program. In the implementation of the Smart Indonesia Program funding, there are stages in realizing the desired one, one of which is to prevent children from dropping out of school. This organizational structure is of course for the running of the Smart Indonesia Program as well as to facilitate the disbursement of funds for the Smart Indonesia Program which has several stages including, 1. Proposing the recipients of the Smart Indonesia Program, 2. Management of Funds for the Smart Indonesia Program recipients, 3. Determination of Smart Indonesia Program recipients and 4. Determination of Smart Indonesia Card recipients.

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